

The conception of Abuja - the new Capital City of Nigeria - as synthesis of planning principles from Europe, America and Japan

Introduction

Abuja is not only the latest, but also one of the most high-flying projects of a new capital, not only in a developing country. Its foundation had been initiated in 1975. The execution of the plan lags behind the schedule, but the project is going forward, and the transfer from Lagos to Abuja has formally been declared in 1991. Meanwhile the growing city has taken over important political institutions.

Basically, the realization of Abuja still follows the original master-plan without fundamental modifications for nearly 25 years, although spontaneous settlements in the surroundings, not having been planned, also came into existence.

The planning of the new capital was strongly influenced by foreign arrangements. The conception really is a work of town- and landscape-planners of industrial nations. The foundation took place during a time, when the planners were hardly engaged to find new theoretical models of whole cities but focussed on solutions for a socially and ecologically sustainable redevelopment. In the case of Abuja the question therefore arises in which way not very up-to-date town-planning principles were used due to lack of new concepts. These guidelines are largely maintained during the long-lasting process of realization of the city, although there were changing general intentions of urban planning in the industrial nations.

The decision for a new capital

The problem of the relocation or new founding of capitals after the colonization of Tropical Africa with the pros and cons of a new start was discussed in many new countries. The motives of alternative foundations result - and this is also the case for Nigeria - mainly from political aims of the young states.

The new capital should

- become a symbol and strengthen the image of Nigeria's aspiration of identity and greatness.
- contribute to reduce strong ethnic and political contrasts in Nigeria, especially of the Islamic North and the Christian South.
- diminish the functional superiority of the primary city of Lagos.
- lessen regional disparities and be a magnet of "pull"-factors in the "Middle Belt" of Nigeria with low population density.

Planning for Abuja

Location and site

Discussions on a new federal capital to replace Lagos started even before independence, but the realization was not until oil brought an economic boom to Nigeria. Immediately after the coup, which brought him to power in August 1975, the late General Murtala Muhammed set up the Aguda Panel to find a new Federal Capital.

The committee, which set the process of selecting the location in motion, started out with at least 33 candidate sites north of the confluence of the rivers Niger und Benue. In the end, the Federal Capital Territory was chosen in a relatively uninhabited area drawn together administratively from four States. The site had the advantage of being nearly equidistant from the borders, and therefore easily accessible from all parts of the country, and also offers an almost limitless area for expansion.

The area protrudes the humid hot river flats in a height of about 100 to 600 m southwest of the Jos Plateau. A rugged topography with buttes (inselbergs) like Aso Hill would give the city a hilly character. The area belongs to the guinea savannah with pockets of rain forest, woodland savannah and park shrub savannah, and is part of an economically disadvantageous region in comparison with other Nigerian areas. Villagers formerly living there had to evacuate, and were given homes elsewhere to make way for planned development of the city.

Realization of Abuja

The plan of the new city was based on the assumption that, by the end of the 20th century, the city would have a population of 1.6 million and later on an ultimate population of 3.1 million on

an area of 250 km². The whole city was planned to be constructed in four phases. The realization though, went more slowly and Abuja does not even amount to 0.5 million inhabitants nowadays.

At some times the development of the city only advanced very slowly, several crises paralysed the political management. Meanwhile however, after much capital had been invested and partly wasted, the "Operation Abuja" reached the "point of no return". Just recently the growth of the city has consolidated after a relative stagnation.

Layout of Abuja

The efficiency of town planning is normally very slight in Nigeria, with exception of Abuja where the government has at its disposal the total territory of the city. The Federal Capital Development Authority (FCDA) became the government agency being responsible for management, construction, and design of the Federal Capital Territory (FCT).

The plans for Abuja were prepared by the FCDA in corporation with various international experts. The International Planning Associates (IPA) of the USA drew up the city master-plan. The subsequent proposals for the first housing areas were initiated by the Milton Keynes Development Corporation. The urban centre with dominant political buildings was begun by plans of the famous Japanese architect Kenzo Tange in 1981.

The international planners had knowledge about the other prominent projects of town planning, like Brasilia, which was built mainly from 1955 until 1960 in a short-term, or like Milton Keynes, a new town of the "third generation", between Birmingham and London, begun in the 1960s.

The plan of Abuja follows a historically pattern of politically inspired foundation of other new capital cities. A comparison does in fact show some similarities that would lend credence to the feeling that the basic concept of the Abuja plan is somehow related to the one of Brasilia.

The IPA presented a master-plan for a city in the form of a dragon-fly. (Fig.1) The general plan divides the city into two principal parts, the monumental civic axis and the crescent of residential zones, the later in turn divided into two split wings. Both axes give the possibility of future expansion.

By such a construction the "total design" induced a strategy to conduct the expansion of the city over long time through the phases of a module development program. This concept presents a city whose principal pattern and future extent would be evident from the earliest possible moment. The city would be born with an adult skeleton.

Fig.1 – Abuja - Concept Sketch of the New Capital City

1 Central axis

The ground-plan of the master-plan provides the city with a monumental character. The new capital city had to present a sense of unity and national identity. The central area was designed around two important and perpendicular axes, the central axis focussing on Aso Hill, and a much shorter cultural axis. (Fig.2)

The prominent huge granite butte, the Aso Hill should be the most dramatic or easily conspicuous feature in the FCT, which inspite of a distance of nearly thirty-two kilometres, clearly marks a site of particular visual merit. The monumental axis was opposed to Aso Hill, that the three arms zone immediately contrasts scenically. With the background of the hill, it situates a spatially distinct area, which stands out prominently in central location with the national assembly and, sideways in front of it, with the presidential office complex and the supreme court. These buildings were developed rather horizontally than vertically.

The zone of the ministries is south of the three arms; here all governmental institutions will be located around the National Mall, with small several plazas symbolizing each of the national tribes. There are also shops and restaurants intended along stepped terraces, which will provide security to the area after office hours of the ministries.

In the heart of the central area is the location of the municipality, at the crossing of the central axis and the cultural axis, acting as a gate to city-wide activities. This zone situated east and west of this plaza will be composed of those buildings, which are of cultural and religious importance, such as the National Mosque and the National Ecumenical Centre.

The National Plaza will be connected with the Central Business District (CBD) on the central axis, which is composed as a mixed-use area of the central shopping and office centres in high rise buildings. The CBD will also form the nerve centre for all modes of transportation in and out of the city, accommodating an inter-bus terminal and a future railway station.

Fig. 2 - Abuja - Blue Print by Kenzo Tange

Beyond the transportation centre, Kenzo Tange proposed to reserve an area for the extension of the central area along the civic axis for future expansion of the city. In the event of this extension he recommended to include apartment buildings. For that reason he situated the planned sports centre at the far end of this axis, which again would finally be connected directly to the already completed airport.

The central area itself with its linear grid differs from the other development areas. The concept has been over-influenced by a three-dimensional massing of the CBD. The proposed design for the office buildings forms multi-storey-scrappers of about 20 to 40 floors. In this sense it has a strong influence on the observers' or users' perception.

2 Transportation system

The most important single factor in determining the physical organization of the new capital is the arrangement of its transportation facilities. The or-

ganization can be seen as a Cartesian geometric structure, as a backbone structure articulating a rigid zoning system of the developing corridor. The overall plan is organized around two parallel transit corridors, which intersect the central core. (Fig.3)

Fig. 3 - Abuja - Concept Plan of the Street Pattern

The residential areas extend in two directions from the central area and are to link to the city by a system of different types of transit ways. The roads play an important role in determining the phases to develop the wings with residential areas.

3 Residential axes

Some hills surround both the city centre and the residential areas. They will be a boundary to prevent uncontrolled development.

The internal structure of the residential axes follows the idea of a structured and low-density pattern that was principally postulated in the 1930s. Abuja should be a city of a hierarchical sub-division with sectors, districts, and neighbourhoods:

- growth modules in the form of discrete sectors of 12.000 to 15.000 households focused on internal secondary employment centres, and subdivided into residential districts
- residential districts of 6.000 to 10.000 households focused on a hierarchy of commercial, community, and utility services, and organized into a hierarchy of small-scale residential neighbourhoods, which are composed of 500 to 750 households.

There should be a mix of residential representing a range of housing options with respect to size, lo-

cation, and access to service, while concentrating high densities directly adjacent to transit corridors, and lower densities on the periphery.

A citywide open space structure based on a longitudinal parkway system, for which a water course network would be retained for both aesthetic, and drainage purposes, and the surrounding escarpment of hills, which form the visual backdrop to the city, and major focal points within the city.

4 Principles of the Nigerian tradition in the urban structure

The IPA tried to trace that some local tradition had been considered in the master-plan. For that reason they tried to identify a vague formal correspondence of hierarchy in the intra-urban differentiation:

The traditional Nigerian cities exhibit a functional core consisting of three elements: a major open-air market, a government centre of palace and social institutions (usually religious in nature). Around the core elements, which were usually located in the centre of the urban area, the remainder of the urban areas of cities were generally organized around sub-nuclei repetitions of the core elements. There was a mixed land use without clear lines between different functions.

The Nigerian towns though have a much more intimate functional mixture than the hierarchically structured new capital. Altogether, the new city lacks of any noticeable Nigerian lines of tradition. The question arises, whether this was the objective of the officials in the first place, or if they were not probably aiming for a "progressive" modern city of western style.

5 Problems of resettlement

Although Abuja as a growth pole already has a certain economic attraction, the socio-economic contrasts in the Nigerian "Middle Belt" have increased altogether. There are major resettlement problems in the areas surrounding Abuja. Existing settlements have to be given up and moved away. A difficult question is the financial compensation of the resettlers, and the selection of new locations for the settlements. The different stages in the education and civilization on the resettlers have to be considered. Especially the continuous growth of unplanned spontaneous settlements within the town and at its periphery will have negative effects.

Evaluation of Abuja

Particularly firms externally made the master-plan of Abuja, from Western countries. The most guidelines from the viewpoint of town-planning are evidently corresponding international principles.

The planners - like in Brasilia - should have been engaged in the imageability by the creation of a city in which the observer would be able to perceive the purpose, organization and symbolism of the various important functions of the new capital.

Brasilia and Abuja have two crossing axes. The wings form crescents where the bend is less one in Brasilia than one in Abuja. The intersection of the two major axes creates the location of the central core. The further divisions of Abuja into sectors, districts, and neighbourhoods are more similar to new towns in Britain.

In Abuja and in Brasilia two main town-planning guidelines were combined:

- the principle of the functional segregation, as in 1933 Le Corbusier has put it in the Charta of Athens. The different functions are divided into homogeneous activity zones, linked by transportation facilities. The IPA also intended the functional division within the central city of Abuja, but that at least was slightly moderated there by the definite plan of Kenzo Tange.
- the idea of "neighbourhood units", which was explicated by Clarence Perry in 1925, and especially applied to British new towns with a hierarchical structure of centrality and road traffic.

Meanwhile the term "neighbourhood unit" mostly disappeared from the vocabulary, and from the concepts of the planners. However, the intention of a separation of urban territory by main traffic lines, and its structural division by green space belong to general accepted planning intentions.

Abuja has been conceived as a national monument as well as the new capital visually symbolises a degree of mechanisation, which Nigeria has not achieved but seeks as a national goal.

A new capital is primarily a city with an environment in which a large number of social and economic activities should be effectively interrelated. The planning though, does not lie in an ecological scenario of a city-to-be. The general efforts to gain a sustainable city or of the "ville durable" have not yet been completely realized in any model of the land use pattern, and thus not in Abuja nowadays.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abumere, S.I. (1981), The people's choice: resettlement preferences of displaced persons from Nigeria's new Federal Capital Territory. - In: *Ekistics* 291, S.476-480.
- Adekunle, A. (1985), *Geography of the New Nigeria Capital - Abuja*. Polytechnic Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Bettinotti, M. (1996), *Kenzo Tange 1946-1996. Architecture and urban design*. - *architettura e disegno urbano*. Milano: Electa.
- Dantata, M. (1999), *Abuja. A business travel guide*. Abuja.

Ehotiyon Associates Int. (Nigeria) Limited (1994), *Integrated Regional Plan and implementation strategies for the FCT. The planning environment. Progress Report.* Ibadan.

Federal Capital Development Authority (1986a), *Abuja. The making of a new capital for Nigeria.* Abuja.

Federal Capital Development Authority (1986b), *General landscape concept. Final Report Phase 1.* Abuja.

Federal Capital Development Authority & Doxiades Associates (1983), *Regional development plan for the Federal Capital Territory.* Lagos.

Heise, H. (2000), *Zielsetzung und Realisierung der neuen Hauptstadt Abuja, Nigeria.* Thesis Universität Hamburg. Hamburg.

Ikejiyor, U. (1996), Land for housing und development control issues in Abuja.- In: *Ekistics* 376, S.143-151.

International Planning Associates (1978), *Site evaluation and site selection. Report N. 2.* Lagos.

International Planning Associates (1979), *The masterplan for Abuja, the New Federal Capital of Nigeria.* Lagos.

International Planning Associates (1983), *The Federal Capital Territory. General land use plans and landscape guidelines. Final Report.* Lagos.

Jardin & Développement & Associates Ltd (1982), *Abuja, Federal Capital City. General landscape concept. Final Report Phase I.*

Manshard, W. (1986), Die neuen Hauptstädte Tropisch-Afrikas. - In: *Zeitschrift für Wirtschaftsgeographie* 30, S. 1-13

Moore, J. (1984), The political history of Nigeria's new capital. - In: *The Journal of Modern African Studies* 22, S.167-175.

Olarewaju, T.O. (1991), *Development control activities in Abuja: problems and prospects.* Dissertation University of Ibadan. Ibadan.

Sabo Ago, A.U. (1999), *Implementation of masterplan. The Abuja experience 1979-1999.* - Paper presented at the workshop on "The review of Abuja master-plan", 29. Nov. - 1. Dez. 1999 Abuja. Abuja.

Tange, K. & URTEC (1981), *Central area urban design of Abuja, the New Capital City.* Abuja.

The University of Ibadan Consultancy Services (1991), *Development indicators and village mergers for accelerated economic development in the Federal Capital Territory.* Final Report. Ibadan.

Todd, T.A. (1980), Nigeria plans its New Capital. - In: *Urban Design International* 1, S.12-17.

U.N. University Tokyo & Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research (1984), *Papers presented at the "Workshop on the planning of capital cities in developing countries" in Abuja, 4.-9. March 1984.* Abuja.

Vagale, L.R. (1976), *The form and structure of new capital cities: Guidelines for the design and development of the proposed Federal Capital of Nigeria.* Nigerian Institute of Town Planning. Seventh Annual Conference. Ibadan 11-13 Nov.1976. Ibadan.

Vale, L.J. (1992), *Architecture, power, and national identity.* New Haven/London: Yale University Press.

Jürgen Lafrens, born on 1.5.1938 in Hamburg, since 1985 Professor of Geograpy at the University of Hamburg, since 1992 Director of the Institute of Geography. Reseach: Urban geography. Urban planning history. Urban historical cartography, Various publications on urban, genetic and town planning, subject, among them the analysis on the development of town-plans and townscape, the urban projects during the Facismo in European Countries, the revitalization of city cores and of post-industrial waterfronts. Editor: *Deutscher Städteatlas (Atlas of German Towns)*, author of the last volume: *Weimar (first town of the Bauhaus)*. DOCOMOMO membership since 1995 (Interest: Urbanism, especially Townscape)

KEYWORDS

Abuja, Capital City, international planning principles